

Panthera leo Tawny lion (African lion)

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Mammal

Size:

Males:	Length: 2.5-3.3 m	Shoulder Height: 1.2 m	Mass: 150-225 kg
Females:	Length: 2.3-2.7 m	Shoulder Height: 1.0 m	Mass: 110-152 kg

Distribution:

The African lion is largely restricted to eastern and southern Africa, with scattered and declining populations elsewhere. Its distribution is far more limited than in the past. They mainly inhabit savannas and grasslands, open woodlands, and semi-arid regions.

Importance:

Lions are classified as vulnerable on the IUCN Red List. They face threats such as habitat loss and human-lion conflicts. There are no previous annotated African lion genomes available.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 115.83 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 10 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 2.45 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 100% [Single: 94.5%, Duplicated: 5.5%]
BUSCO database: eukaryota
Assembly N50: 108 499.01 kilobases
Contig number: 679

Sample Contributor contact details:

Michele A. Miller
Stellenbosch University
miller@sun.ac.za

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